

The “Chicken and the Egg” problem in investment decisions and in particular in the nascent hydrogen economy

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1. Abstract

We investigate the microeconomics of the “chicken and the egg” problem in nascent markets including the question of why it inhibits investment in some markets, but not in others. This is a novel comparative analysis of solution approaches to solve this economical problem.

We create a list of approaches to overcome the two parties chicken and egg problem, categorised in business decisions, psychological, government intervention and market structure. Examples are provided as evidence of these ways to overcome the problem whenever possible. We apply this general theoretical work on the current situation of the nascent green hydrogen economy with a focus on Germany and Saxony-Anhalt.

The results may be helpful for government administrations to overcome the problem in order to accelerate the decarbonisation of the economy or to promote economic growth by accelerating the growth of other nascent markets. Few of the ways out of the problem in this paper do require substantial government funding, which stands in contrast to the dominant approach in literature.¹

Keywords: chicken, egg, hydrogen, microeconomics, risk, market failure, 2PCE

2. Introduction

Markets for new investment goods or new consumables for industrial use may experience an undesirably slow growth because investors face a dilemma: Potential suppliers of such goods may not trust their ability to find buyers and the potential buyers may not trust their ability to find sellers. This may lead to both delay or cancellation of investments.

The term ‘chicken and the egg problem’ is in use to describe this, albeit in variations. It may be shortened to ‘chicken and egg’, ‘chicken or egg’ or ‘chicken-egg’. ‘problem’ may be substituted by the words ‘dilemma’, ‘conundrum’, ‘paradox’, ‘stasis’ and ‘syndrome’. A commonly used German expression for this is “Henne-Ei Problem”.

This problem was first discussed in 1981 and first published in 1984.²

¹ Tuukka Mäkitie et al., ‘Solving the Chicken and Egg Problem in Maritime Hydrogen Value Chains in Western Norway’, FME NTRANS Report (Norwegian Centre for Energy Transition Strategies, 2021), <https://www.ntnu.edu/documents/1276062818/1283878281/Solving+the+chicken+and+egg+problem+in+maritime+hydrogen+value+chains+in+Western+Norway.pdf/>.

² Daniel Sperling, *New Transportation Fuels: A Strategic Approach towards Technological Change* (University of California Press, 1988), 510.

Sperling described the problem as “This metaphor may be generalized to any situation in which it is presumed that first, in order for a new product to be widely accepted, two or more major investment activities must proceed concurrently, and second, that unless an independent but complementary investment is also made, no investment will be made. Obviously, there would be a paralysis of investments because the initial commitment for one set of investments would be contingent on a commitment for the other; neither commitment would be forthcoming because of the great risk associated with making the initial commitment”.³

White et al gave an example scenario of the chicken and egg problem in the hydrogen economy; “(...) a firm wishing to invest in green hydrogen production to meet export demand will need access to reliable and sufficient renewable electricity capacity, a domestic delivery network and export facilities, and will need to be sure that global supply chains are in place and importers have the required facilities. The firm may not be willing to proceed with its investment if this infrastructure is not in place—however the same is true of investors in other aspects of the supply chain. This uncertainty is increased by the fact there are no global hydrogen supply chains to build on (...)”⁴ and also pointed out that the problem may also occur with labour with specialised qualifications.⁵

Much of the earlier research about the chicken and the egg problem in hydrogen markets had a focus on hydrogen-powered road vehicles, which require vehicle manufacturers, vehicle users and infrastructure (fueling stations) providers. Some of this research suggested establishing infrastructure first and focused on modelling how much infrastructure would be needed to kick-start the sector.⁶ Ultimately, hydrogen-powered road vehicles appear to be no more than niche solutions⁷ due to lacking infrastructure and the cost inefficiency of their technical approach compared to other vehicles.⁸

Governments and non-government organisations stated that the green hydrogen economy is affected by the chicken and egg problem.⁹ Green hydrogen is a term describing hydrogen

3 Daniel Sperling, *New Transportation Fuels: A Strategic Approach towards Technological Change* (University of California Press, 1988), 365.

4 Lee V. White, David Gourlay, and Emma Aisbett, ‘Chapter 1.2 Potential Market Failures Inhibiting the Development of a Green Hydrogen Export Industry’, in *Towards Hydrogen Infrastructure: Advances and Challenges in Preparing for the Hydrogen Economy* (Elsevier, 2023), 39–58.

5 White, Gourlay, and Aisbett.

6 M. Melendez and A. Milibrandt, ‘Hydrogen Infrastructure Transition Analysis’ (National Renewable Energy Laboratory, January 2006), <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy06osti38351.pdf>.

7 ‘IDTechEx Predicts Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles to Be 4% of the Zero Emission Solution in 2044’, *Green Car Congress* (blog), 7 January 2024, <https://www.greencarcongress.com/2024/01/20240107-fcev.html>.

8 Andrew F. Burke, Jingyuan Zhao, and Lewis M. Fulton, ‘Projections of the Costs of Light-Duty Battery-Electric and Fuel Cell Vehicles (2020–2040) and Related Economic Issues’, *Research in Transportation Economics* 105 (1 July 2024): 101440, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2024.101440>.

9 ‘Hydrogen in Latin America’ (International Energy Agency, August 2021), 14, <https://www.iea.org/reports/hydrogen-in-latin-america>; ‘UK Hydrogen Strategy’, 17 August 2021, 10, https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/64c7e8bad8b1a70011b05e38/UK-Hydrogen-Strategy_web.pdf; ‘Understanding the Realities of Hydrogen: Key Insights From the IEA Report’, *Fuel Cell Works* (blog), 16 January 2025, <https://fuelcellworks.com/2025/01/16/hydrogen/understanding-the-realities-of-hydrogen-key-insights-from-the-iea-report>.

produced from water using renewable energies.¹⁰ The use of this consumable has a reduced greenhouse gas footprint compared to fossil fuel alternatives¹¹ and is thus an important candidate for the decarbonisation of the economy. Hydrogen can be used as material input and as energy carrier. In the latter function it's cheaper than rechargeable batteries at large scale for storing energy for electricity supply.¹² Hydrogen may also be used to generate high temperatures process heat¹³ when electrification of the process heat generation is not viable. Hydrogen has been produced, handled and consumed for generations, but the dominant method for generating hydrogen gas is steam reforming;¹⁴ a process that splits off hydrogen from natural gas and releases large amounts of greenhouse gases. Their emission is very undesirable due to the damages caused by the anthropogenic manipulation of the climate.¹⁵

A green hydrogen value chain requires renewable electricity generation, power lines, transformers, electrolysers, equipment to compress hydrogen, pipelines and their pumps, small (pressurized cylindrical or spherical containers) or large (underground caverns) hydrogen storage capacity, safety and testing tools, equipment to make use of the hydrogen and around all this the suppliers for these investment goods.

The European Union's carbon pricing scheme is a foundational incentive to decarbonise the economies in the EU.¹⁶ It not only motivates a move from the natural gas-derived grey hydrogen to green hydrogen, but also other conversion processes away from processes involving fossil fuels to such involving green hydrogen. 108 Governments have committed to aims of decarbonising the economies, usually before or till the year 2050.¹⁷ The chicken and the egg problem is important, because it appears to slow down the conversion towards green hydrogen-involving processes and thus the decarbonisation as a whole.

3. The “Chicken and the egg” problem in theory

3.1 Definition of the two parties chicken and the egg problem

The two parties chicken and the egg problem (henceforth called “2PCE”) can be defined as both potential sellers and potential buyers of a good refrain from committing to their

10 Jimena Incer-Valverde et al., “Colors” of Hydrogen: Definitions and Carbon Intensity’, *Energy Conversion and Management* 291 (1 September 2023): 117294, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2023.117294>.

11 Incer-Valverde et al.

12 Ning Qi et al., ‘Long-Term Energy Management for Microgrid with Hybrid Hydrogen-Battery Energy Storage: A Prediction-Free Coordinated Optimization Framework’, *Applied Energy* 377 (1 January 2025): 124485, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.124485>.

13 ‘Global Hydrogen Review 2024’ (International Energy Agency, October 2024), 154f, <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/89c1e382-dc59-46ca-aa47-9f7d41531ab5/GlobalHydrogenReview2024.pdf>.

14 IEA, ‘Global Hydrogen Review 2024’, 10 January 2024, <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-hydrogen-review-2024>.

15 ‘Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change’ (Geneva, Switzerland: International Panel on Climate Change, 20 March 2023),

https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_SYR_FullVolume.pdf.

16 ‘DIRECTIVE 2003/87/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL’ (2003), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32003L0087>.

17 ‘Net-Zero Tracker’, 8 April 2025, <https://www.climatewatchdata.org/net-zero-tracker>.

necessary capacity investments because they doubt that the respective other side of the potential trade commits to their necessary investments in time. The potential buyers fear a lack of supply and the potential suppliers fears a lack of demand.

Extended versions of the 2PCE problem could exist if the supply and demand bottlenecks extend over more than two directly consecutive value chain levels or if the two bottleneck levels are separated by an intermediate level that's no bottleneck.¹⁸ We don't discuss these cases.

3.2 Similar economic problems

The three parties chicken and the egg problem can be defined as an intermediary having difficulty to motivate buyers and sellers to use his platform while it has no critical mass of either buyers or sellers yet. This problem doesn't necessarily involve an investment hold-up. The term "two-sided markets" is in use to describe such constellations. Typical examples are the introduction of an online trading platform and the introduction of a new debit or credit card standard.

An extended interpretation of a chicken and egg problem was used by IRENA when they stated that small production volumes lead to high prices at which too little demand exists while economies of scale are needed to reach low prices. We don't cover this version of a chicken and egg problem.¹⁹

The first of a kind (FOAK) problem is focused on the economic viability problems that a first adopter faces. This includes especially teething problems of the technology. FOAK plants may be demonstrators without commercial viability, built to reduce the risks of a wider adoption.²⁰ FOAK investments do face the 2PCE problem, but the additional technical risks justify a treatment of the FOAK as a different problem or usually rather a bundle of problems. FOAK may include the chicken and the egg problem, but it certainly includes other challenges such as technical risk as well. The two parties chicken and the egg problem may still depress a value chain's growth long after a FOAK plant succeeded technically or even commercially.

Another similar problem is the hold-up problem. "In a standard hold-up problem, there are two parties who tomorrow can generate a surplus. One of the two parties can today make an investment in order to increase the surplus that can be generated tomorrow. [...] If the investing party has all the bargaining power tomorrow, it will extract the total surplus generated in the relationship, so today it has first-best investment incentives. However, if the

18 Tobias Sprenger, Amir Ashour Novirdourst, et al., 'The Power of Scale Economies of Scale and the Hydrogen Value Chain' (Institute of Energy Economics at the University of Cologne (EWI), 6 January 2023), 26, https://www.ewi.uni-koeln.de/cms/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/20230602_EWI_The-Power-of-Scale_Economies-of-Scale-and-the-Hydrogen-Value-Chain.pdf.

19 Emanuele Bianco and Diala Hawila, 'Solving the Chicken and Egg Problem: Auctions for Green Hydrogen', *IRENA Newsletter*, 12 September 2021, <https://www.irena.org/News/expertinsights/2021/Sep/Auctions-for-Green-Hydrogen>.

20 Chris Bataille, Seton Stiebert, and Jonas Algers, 'Triggering Investment in First-of-a-Kind and Early Near-Zero Emissions Industrial Facilities', *Morningside Campus Status Updates* (Center on Global Energy Policy at Columbia SIPA, 1 August 2024), <https://www.energypolicy.columbia.edu/publications/triggering-investment-in-first-of-a-kind-and-early-near-zero-emissions-industrial-facilities/>.

investing party has no bargaining power tomorrow, then the other party will extract the total surplus, so that today the investment incentives are zero.”²¹ “Hold-up problem” is the economic term for investment inhibition by fear of worsening one’s bargaining power by investing first and having sunk costs, whereas the 2PCE problem is about a fear of not getting enough or affordable inputs or not being able to sell one’s output after investing to build up production.

Herding, herd behavior and penguin effect are terms used to describe another kind of investment hold-up. Potential investors may refrain from investing because they don’t want to stand out as having failed when others avoided risk or because waiting for others to fail or succeed reduces the risk of the own investment plan.²² Choi described his version of herd behaviour as “Herd behavior [...] is driven by the fear of being stranded. Experimentation with a new technology is avoided because of the informational consequences accompanying the adoption of an untested technology.”²³

The term “Counterparty risk” is used to express that a contract partner may not fulfil its obligations. The 2PCE problem on the other hand is a pre-contract problem.

3.3 A risk management problem

The 2PCE problem is largely an effect of Knightian uncertainty.²⁴

The investors delay or cancel the entry into the value chain because they fear the economic losses after entering a poorly or non-functioning market with a largely irreversible investment. A potential supplier might invest in his ability to provide the good, but might then find himself incapable of selling it in quantity for years, accumulating losses due to capital costs and having opportunity costs from not allocating his resources into alternative investment opportunities. A potential buyer might invest in his ability to make use of the good, but might then find himself incapable of procuring enough input.

The identification of the 2PCE problem as being at its core a risk management problem opens up possible pathways to solve the problem through risk mitigation. Risk can in theory be described with an expectation value, the product of probability of the risk being realised and severity of damage when the risk is being realised.

3.4 The role of information asymmetry

Potential investors wait because they doubt the timely investment of other potential investors. One might suspect an information asymmetry problem in this. Four cases should be

21 Katja Franke et al., ‘Assessing Worldwide Future Potentials of Renewable Electricity Generation: Installable Capacity, Full Load Hours and Costs’, *Renewable Energy* 226, no. C (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.120>.

22 Jay Pil Choi, ‘Herd Behavior, the “Penguin Effect,” and the Suppression of Informational Diffusion: An Analysis of Informational Externalities and Payoff Interdependency’, *The RAND Journal of Economics* 28, no. 3 (1997): 407–25, <https://doi.org/10.2307/2556022>; David S. Scharfstein and Jeremy C. Stein, ‘Herd Behavior and Investment’, *The American Economic Review* 80, no. 3 (1990): 465–79.

23 Choi, ‘Herd Behavior, the “Penguin Effect,” and the Suppression of Informational Diffusion’.

24 Frank Hyneman Knight, *Risk, Uncertainty and Profit* (Boston and New York: Houghton Mifflin Company The Riverside Press Cambridge, 1921), <https://fraser.stlouisfed.org/files/docs/publications/books/risk/riskuncertaintyprofit.pdf>.

examined:

Information asymmetry in which an intention to invest is unknown

The 2PCE problem was already overcome when this intention was formed. It's now in the best interest of the investor to inform the potential investors who might become his suppliers or customers of this decision in order to motivate them to invest as well. This is not a 2PCE problem situation.

Information asymmetry in which neither potential investor intends to invest

This is the 2PCE problem case and we see neither how information asymmetry could help in solving it nor how it could help to sustain it.

Perfect information in which an intention to invest is known

This should be in practice equivalent to the outcome of the first case, as the investors are motivated to announce his investment in said case, thus providing sufficient information about their intent.

Perfect information in which neither potential investor intends to invest

This is the most interesting case, for in this case the potential investors are just as discouraged from investing as in the second case. They know for certain about the lack of supply or demand for their envisaged business model's output and it's going to take one of the 2PCE problem solutions of chapter four to overcome the investment hold-up.

The 2PCE problem is thus not dependent on information asymmetry.

3.5 Is the “chicken and the egg” problem a market failure?

Several definitions of market failure have been proposed and used in economics. Brian Dollery and Joseph Wallis (2001) wrote “In generic terms market failure may be defined as the inability of a market or system of markets to provide goods and services either at all or in an economically optimal manner. It is possible to define market failure more precisely in terms of allocative efficiency. For instance, from a Pigouvian perspective, market failure occurs when marginal social costs do not coincide with marginal social benefits for a particular good or service. Put differently, market failure occurs when market prices do not equate with marginal social costs. This means that market prices as signalling devices will not accurately reflect the full social costs of producing the economic good in question and so producers will either under- or over-produce the good.”²⁵

Charles Wolf (1986) identified four kinds of market failures; externalities and public goods, increasing returns, market imperfections and distributional equity.²⁶

The 2PCE problem may sometimes be a market failure, depending on whether overcoming it improves allocative efficiency. The 2PCE problem is capable of keeping the market from providing the goods at all and it's capable of reducing allocative efficiency. This happens

25 Brian Dollery and Joe Wallis, ‘The Theory of Market Failure and Policy Making in Contemporary Local Government’, March 2001, 9, https://www.une.edu.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0010/67816/econwp01-6.pdf.

26 Charles Wolf, ‘Markets or Governments: Choosing between Imperfect Alternatives’ (The Rand Corporation, September 1986), 14–24, <https://www.rand.org/content/dam/rand/pubs/notes/2006/N2505.pdf> pp 14-24.

when potential investors intend to invest in a profitable investment project (due to the 2PCE problem not being solved yet), regardless of perfect, partial or no information.

Market failures are considered to be reasons for government intervention in markets, so the identification of the 2PCE problem as a market failure in a specific case could be used as a justification for government intervention to solve the problem.²⁷ Government intervention in regard to the hydrogen value chain's 2PCE problem was justified with the externalities problem of greenhouse gas emissions and the resulting desire to decarbonise GHG-emitting processes.²⁸

4. Solutions to the "Chicken and the egg" problem

The solutions to the 2PCE problem can be categorised into business decisions, psychological, government intervention and market structure solutions.

Figure 1 Solution approaches to the 2PCE problem, own research

4.1 Business decisions

4.1.1 Vertical integration

The problem can be solved if the potential investor of the demand side decides to vertically

²⁷ Wolf, 'Markets or Governments: Choosing between Imperfect Alternatives'.

²⁸ Mäkitie et al., 'Solving the Chicken and Egg Problem in Maritime Hydrogen Value Chains in Western Norway'; 'UK Hydrogen Strategy', 9–10.

integrate the production of his needed precursor supply or if the potential investor of the supply side decides to vertically integrate the consumption of his precursor production. An example for this is the Salzgitter AG's plan to reduce the carbon emissions of its steelmaking with the direct reduction method. This includes the plan to use the precursor consumable hydrogen and plans for the company to produce a reliable supply of hydrogen with an electrolyser system on-site.²⁹ A joint venture of Shell and other companies attempted to use the vertical integration solution to solve the 2PCE problem for the hydrogen fuel-fuel stations-road vehicles challenge that spans three value chain levels, but faced the poor economics of hydrogen-fuelled road vehicles.³⁰

Research has indicated that vertical integration can also add to an investment hold-up issue in a market, though.³¹

4.1.2 Cooperation for coordination

Another solution is for the potential investors to get in contact with potential investors of the corresponding value chain level and cooperate to coordinate the investments. This reduces the uncertainty and creates confidence in the timely existence of supply of and demand for the good. An example for this is Everfuel A/S' LoI to supply up to 10,000 tons of hydrogen annually beginning in 2028 to a green hydrogen offtaker.³² Another example is the effort to build up to 500 MW electrolysis capacity to feed hydrogen to ammonia production in Piesteritz, Saxony-Anhalt (Germany).³³ The Green Power MSH2 project in Saxony-Anhalt (Germany) is another example.³⁴

4.1.3 Marketplace for future contracts

A third party can organise a marketplace for futures contracts or double-sided auctions that brings potential supply investors and potential demand investors together. An example in the area of green hydrogen is the Hintco double-sided auction, albeit it attempts a combination of this solution with government intervention backing.³⁵ It's the European Commission's policy to connect EU domestic hydrogen supply and demand through fixed premium auctions via

29 'GrInHy2.0: Grüner Wasserstoff Für Grüne Stahlproduktion', *Salzgitter AG Press Releases*, 17 October 2022, <https://www.salzgitter-ag.com/de/newsroom/pressemeldungen/details/grinhy20-gruener-wasserstoff-fuer-gruene-stahlproduktion-20194.html>.

30 'Shell Venture Eyes Creating Hydrogen Supply and Demand', *Argus Media* (blog), 11 October 2021, <https://www.argusmedia.com/en/news-and-insights/latest-market-news/2262465-shell-venture-eyes-creating-hydrogen-supply-and-demand>.

31 M.-L. Allain, C. Chambole, and P. Rey, 'Vertical Integration as a Source of Hold-Up', *Review of Economic Studies* 83, no. 1 (2016): 1–25, <https://doi.org/10.1093/restud/rdv035>; Marie-Laure Allain et al., 'Vertical Integration as a Source of Hold-up: An Experiment', *European Economic Review* 137 (1 August 2021): 103783, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurocorev.2021.103783>.

32 'Everfuel Signs Letter of Intent with German Industrial Offtaker for Initial Supply of 10,000 Tons of Green Hydrogen per Year', *Everfuel Press Releases* (blog), 8 May 2024, <https://www.everfuel.com/news/everfuel-signs-letter-of-intent-with-german-industrial-offtaker-for-initial-supply-of-10000-tons-of-green-hydrogen-per-year/>.

33 'VNG Und HyCC Planen Erzeugung von Grünem Wasserstoff in Lutherstadt Wittenberg | VNG AG', accessed 9 May 2025, <https://www.vng.de/de/newsroom/2024-12-04-vng-und-hycc-planen-erzeugung-von-gruenem-wasserstoff-lutherstadt-wittenberg>.

34 'Green Power MSH2', accessed 15 April 2025, <https://www.stadtwerke-hettstedt.de/ihr-service/downloads/energietagung.html?file=files/downloads/1-energietagung/presesi-seg-green-power-msh2.pdf>.

35 'Hintco Factsheet', accessed 9 April 2025, <https://cdn.sanity.io/files/u4w9plcz/production/8506bc6f24909ba96b6748f3fb0b28ab914607da.pdf>.

the Hydrogen bank.³⁶ India also used a tender model to bring together supply and demand regarding green ammonia (a green hydrogen derivative).³⁷

4.1.4 Incremental investment

The investments to supply or to make use of the different goods can be made in small, incremental steps. Each of these investment steps may fail, but the severity of the failure would be acceptable. The incremental approach has the additional benefits of partially exploiting the value in waiting to invest³⁸ and of requiring only a much easier-to-achieve build-up of a competent workforce.

McDonald/Siegel gave a concise reason why there's a value in waiting to invest: "The decision to build the plant is irreversible; the plant cannot be used for any other purpose. The decision to defer building, however, is reversible. This asymmetry, when properly taken into account, leads to a rule that says build the plant only if benefits exceed costs by a certain positive amount."³⁹ So there's a risk premium to investment decisions because of opportunity costs, and incremental investment reduces how much risk premium an investor has to accept at a time.

The incremental investment solution is particularly possible to very large corporations, for even big investment failures may not endanger their survival.

4.1.5 Risk pooling

A related approach is to not reduce the project size, but to widen the shoulders that support it. The uncertainty would be managed through risk pooling. Insurances use reinsurers to manage their non-systemic risks in bigger risk pools is the classic example for the risk management approach of risk pooling. H₂-News interpreted intersectoral cooperation as a version of risk pooling.⁴⁰

4.2 Psychological

4.2.1 Social pressure to invest

Song et al. covered the topic of social pressure on businesses to adopt a higher purpose.⁴¹ It is imaginable that social pressure may sufficiently motivate a company to invest and thus overcome the 2PCE problem. Chan et al. published a model about green investment for societal well-being⁴² and Jing-Yue et al. wrote about the motivation for green investment by

36 'COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS', 16 March 2023, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52023DC0156>.

37 Amish A., 'A Lot of Firsts in the India Green Ammonia Auction', June 2024, <https://www.vnzinsights.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Indias-Green-Ammonia-Auction-SIGHT-Tender.pdf>.

38 Robert McDonald and Daniel Siegel, 'The Value of Waiting to Invest*', *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 101, no. 4 (1 November 1986): 707–27, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1884175>.

39 McDonald and Siegel.

40 'Henne-Ei-Problem', *H2-news.de* (blog), accessed 15 April 2025, <https://h2-news.de/glossary/henne-ei/>.

41 Fenghua Song, Anjan Thakor, and Robert Quinn, 'Purpose, Profit and Social Pressure', *Journal of Financial Intermediation* 55 (1 July 2023): 101031, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfi.2023.101031>.

42 Kar Hoong Chan et al., 'A Model of Green Investment Decision Making for Societal Well-Being', *Heliyon* 8, no. 8 (1 August 2022): e10024, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e10024>.

societal pressure.⁴³ A joint investment fund including Total energies showed that such efforts can reach substantial financial strength.⁴⁴

4.2.2 Mistake or negligence

Calculations may be incorrect, due diligence procedures may be neglected, a manager about to leave a company may want to make his legacy more ethical with one last big investment decision.

4.2.3 Delusion

Propaganda, hype, group thinking and biases may lead to decisions different from a rational decision. The introduction of methanol, compressed hydrogen and natural gas fuelled road vehicles in spite of lacking infrastructure and high costs may have been grounded on such delusions. The overcapacities for production of very specialised electrolysis equipment in 2024 may have been caused by the hype around hydrogen.⁴⁵

4.2.4 Willingness to carry a risk

Willingness to carry a risk can help break a hold-up that's in considerable part caused by uncertainty. An example is the behaviour of Geopura Ltd..⁴⁶

Some decision makers are risk-seeking rather than risk-neutral or risk-averse.⁴⁷ Feelings influence risk-taking.⁴⁸ The decision-maker is always human, not a homo oeconomicus. This may lead to decisions in favour of a final investment decision even when a rational approach would judge against it.

4.3 Government intervention

4.3.1 Incentives

A government can give various incentives to encourage investment in a 2PCE problem-affected value chain aside from becoming a buyer itself.⁴⁹ Incentives include but are not limited to tax credits, direct subsidies, competition prizes, manipulation of write-off rules and privileges. Rodrick pointed out that subsidies can be limited to ex ante subsidies whenever the value chain is profitable once established.⁵⁰ Arnaiz del Pozo et al. concluded

43 Jing-Yue Liu et al., 'Resistance or Motivation? Impact of Climate Risk on Corporate Greenwashing: An Empirical Study of Chinese Enterprises', *Global Finance Journal* 62 (1 September 2024): 101030, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfj.2024.101030>.

44 'TotalEnergies, Air Liquide, VINCI and a Group of International Companies Launch the World's Largest Clean Hydrogen Infrastructure Fund', TotalEnergies.com, 10 January 2021, <https://totalenergies.com/media/news/press-releases/launch-of-the-worlds-largest-clean-hydrogen-infrastructure-fund>.

45 Strategy&, 'Battle on the Global Electrolyzer Market', Strategy&, accessed 15 April 2025, <https://www.strategyand.pwc.com/de/en/industries/energy-utilities/electrolyzer-market.html>.

46 Lukanyo Mnyanda, 'Cracking Green Hydrogen's Chicken and Egg Problem', *Financial Times*, 12 June 2024, sec. Hydrogen power, <https://www.ft.com/content/d3102a61-368e-4ec6-8de3-833f4c62e7ba>.

47 '(PDF) Rational Choice', ResearchGate, accessed 15 April 2025, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227458334_Rational_Choice.

48 '(PDF) Risk As Feelings', *ResearchGate*, 22 October 2024, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/230896630_Risk_As_Feelings.

49 Mäkitie et al., 'Solving the Chicken and Egg Problem in Maritime Hydrogen Value Chains in Western Norway'.

50 Dani Rodrik, 'INDUSTRIAL POLICY FOR THE TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY', September 2004.

governmental incentives for supply and demand would be necessary to overcome the 2PCE problem.⁵¹

4.3.2 Disincentives

Governments may also steer the market actors to invest in a 2PCE-affected value chain by using disincentives. This includes, but is not limited to outlawing or artificially reducing the profitability of substitute products and processes. The EU's Emissions Trading System⁵² may be the main motivation why companies in the EU invest in decarbonization and move towards electrification and green hydrogen at all.

4.3.3 Direct economic investment

Governments can become actors in the 2PCE-affected value chain themselves or through government-controlled businesses investing, buying or trading (purchase and sale) in the value chain. The motivation could be national interests rather than profit. Bento alluded to this in his conclusion by pointing out the analogy of governmental provision of electricity and gas pipeline infrastructures.⁵³

4.3.4 Risk transfer

The possibility of allocating capital to a largely irreversible bad investment is the key inhibitor in the 2PCE problem. The invested capital may be lost and opportunity costs accrue, including not having allocated scarce qualified employees to a better purpose. A government can transfer much of this risk to itself by giving guarantees. It may also guarantee the payment of loans, thus making foreign capital cheaper to the investment project, which may suffice to make it promising enough for a positive final investment decision. The German government extensively uses loan guarantees to subsidise exports.⁵⁴ The IEA claimed that risk transfer could improve the cost of capital for PV projects in Namibia by almost four percent points.⁵⁵

4.3.5 Direct coordination

Rodrick described governments' ability to solve the 2PCE problem (or as he calls it a coordination failure) by "true coordination" of the investments of private businesses.⁵⁶ This may happen by persuasion through communication or by command. Rodrick specifically mentions "Coordination and deliberation council(s)".⁵⁷ Coordination was also mentioned as a possible solution to the 2PCE problem for Northern Ireland.⁵⁸

51 Carlos Arnaiz del Pozo and Schalk Cloete, 'Techno-Economic Assessment of Blue and Green Ammonia as Energy Carriers in a Low-Carbon Future', *Energy Conversion and Management* 255 (March 2022): 115312, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2022.115312>.

52 DIRECTIVE 2003/87/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL.

53 Nuno Bento, 'Building and Interconnecting Hydrogen Networks: Insights from the Electricity and Gas Experience in Europe', *Energy Policy* 36, no. 8 (1 August 2008): 3019–28, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2008.04.007>.

54 'Export Credit Guarantees of the Federal Government', Export Credit Guarantees of the Federal Government, accessed 15 April 2025, <https://www.exportkreditgarantien.de/en>.

55 IEA, 'Global Hydrogen Review 2024', 284.

56 Rodrik, 'INDUSTRIAL POLICY FOR THE TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY'.

57 Rodrik.

58 'Northern-Ireland-Hydrogen-Roadmap-and-Technology-Options-Scoping-Study.Pdf', accessed 15 April 2025, <https://matrixni.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/Northern-Ireland-Hydrogen-Roadmap-and-Technology->

The European parliament stated “One way to mitigate a potential 'chicken and egg' dilemma [...], is by setting sectoral targets”.⁵⁹

4.3.6 Reduction of transaction costs

A government can strive to reduce the transaction costs of private investments in order to promote private investments. This is merely peripherally relevant to the 2PCE problem as a stand-alone approach, but it may be effective as a supporting measure to the mentioned business solutions of information gathering efforts and getting in contact with potential investors.

Possible variations of this are eased regulatory requirements, reduced fees, information dissemination, government-funded and published market research and sponsoring get-together events.

The aforementioned coordination and deliberation councils of Rodrick⁶⁰ can serve to reduce transaction costs by providing an efficient platform for coordination between potential investors.

4.4 Market structure

4.4.1 Substitute supply

The demand side may be able to use substitute inputs. Some steamships used boilers prepared for a mixed firing of oil and coal during the transition of shipping from coal fuel to oil fuel, for example. Some gas turbines are certified for both hydrogen and natural gas fuels. Sperling already implied this solution by pointing out that incompatibility with existing products is a requirement for 2PCE and multifuel vehicles would be an approach to address the chicken-egg problem in regard to introduction of alternative fuels.⁶¹ Amran et al. argued that having the choice of input gives a quantifiable benefit because it improves the bargaining position on top of addressing the input price uncertainties.⁶² The European Commissioner for Climate Action’s support for using blue hydrogen (steam reformed from natural gas with carbon dioxide capture) as substitute for green hydrogen pursued the substitute supply solution for a transition phase.⁶³

4.4.2 Substitute demand

The potential supply-side investor may decide to invest because there’s enough demand for the output outside of a particular value chain. The odds for this increase the better the distribution infrastructure is. An example is the production of wind and photovoltaic power electricity that happens for end users in many industries and at many value chain levels.

Options-Scoping-Study.pdf.

59 ‘Renewable and Low-Carbon Hydrogen’, n.d., 7.

60 Rodrik, ‘INDUSTRIAL POLICY FOR THE TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY’.

61 Sperling, *New Transportation Fuels: A Strategic Approach towards Technological Change*, 366, 367, 386.

62 ‘Infrastructure12.Pdf’, accessed 15 April 2025, <https://people.bu.edu/nalink/papers/Infrastructure12.pdf>.

63 Frédéric Simon, ‘EU Bets on Blue Hydrogen “to Break Chicken-and-Egg Problem”’, Euractiv, 9 December 2020, <https://www.euractiv.com/section/energy-environment/news/eu-bets-on-blue-hydrogen-to-break-chicken-and-egg-problem/>.

4.4.3 Sufficient co-product revenue

The potential supply-side investor may decide in favour of the investment if co-products yield enough revenue to meet his requirements for a positive final investment decision. This would break up a 2PCE situation for a particular co-product. The first oil refineries benefitted from such a situation, as the markets for many oil refinery co-products of today only developed generations later.

4.4.4 Confidence in transport infrastructure

A potential investor may be satisfied with the prospect of finding a supplier or customer somewhere in a very large transportation grid without being able to pinpoint ensured supply or demand from specific companies or having a market report indicating satisfactorily probable excess demand or excess supply. The effort required to collect information about all suppliers and all demanders connected to a continental distribution infrastructure and the effort required to process all that information are impractically high for almost all actors.

An example is a continent-wide pipeline network that connects so many companies that only the biggest companies could afford to conduct thorough market research about the near-future supply or demand situation. The authorised 9,040 km of German backbone pipeline for interregional transportation of hydrogen gas⁶⁴ may solve the chicken-egg problem for those potential hydrogen consumers in Germany that can economically be connected to it. H₂-News mentioned this solution in its short list of possible 2PCE problem solutions in the form of international cooperation to create bigger markets.⁶⁵

4.5 Other

Very rich private persons or non-government organisations could hypothetically emulate the government solutions of funding and risk transfer with philanthropic motivation. Examples for this are philanthropic contributions to H2Global (Hintco).⁶⁶

Finally, the profit expectations for a functioning market could be so high that an investment proposal is attractive enough even with a very high probability of failure due to unavailable demand or supply.

4.6 Solution combinations

Several solutions approaches can be and were combined.

H2Global's Hintco scheme combines reduction of transaction costs, government incentives, marketplace for futures contracts, philanthropy⁶⁷ and H2Global considers a risk pooling feature⁶⁸ on the background of government disincentives (EU ETS), for example. This makes it considerably more difficult to find pure examples for evidence for successful 2PCE solutions, especially as carbon emissions trading schemes (government intervention disincentives) cover most large economies and affect trade.

64 'Bundesnetzagentur - Wasserstoff-Kernnetz', accessed 15 April 2025, <https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/DE/Fachthemen/ElektrizitaetundGas/Wasserstoff/Kernnetz/start.html>.

65 'Henne-Ei-Problem'.

66 Timo Böllerhey, 'The 2nd H2Global Hydrogen Auction', <https://mission-hydrogen.com/webinarlibrary/>.

67 Böllerhey.

68 Hanna Graul, 'Re: Re: Frage zu Hintco', 3 June 2025.

Clusters called hydrogen valleys have been proposed as a solution to the chicken-egg problem.⁶⁹ This is within our framework potentially a combination of cooperation for coordination, reduction of transaction costs and if the cluster is big enough an analogy to confidence in transport infrastructure.

4.7 Inhibiting factors to solving the 2PCE problem

We reason that a single small investor investing in a potential value chain for either supply or demand cannot solve the entire 2PCE problem continent-wide. Such a small capital investment may enable a local matching (supply for demand or vice versa) follow-up capital investment, though. A single small investment in capacity creating supply or demand in the value chain may not have any effect if the good can be transported well (such as an investment in the hydrogen economy with connection to a continent-spanning pipeline network that's still lacking supply and demand and suffering from the 2PCE problem), for its size may be negligible in an interregional context. It may require the observation of many natural experiments to discern at what level of investment relative to the overall size of the potential market or other possibly decisive variables investments become quantitatively capable of solving the 2PCE problem.

Another possible inhibition to a 2PCE problem solution may be mutually neutralising investments in supply and demand. A very large potential market as a whole would likely not get kickstarted decisively if a capital investment creates an industrial process creating demand and in the same stroke also just enough on-site supply for the process. The vertical integration would in such a case solve the 2PCE problem exclusively for this investor or joint venture, not for other investors in the potential value chain.

These first two inhibiting factors lead to the conclusion that an increase of supply or demand can solve the 2PCE problem in three ways; much excess supply or much excess demand solve it for the whole market, while other efforts can only solve the problem for one or few companies, possibly for a pre-defined club of cooperating companies (such as in a microgrid).

A third inhibition is the issue of time lags. Time lags in communication, time lags in processing and verifying the communicated intent, time lags in decision-making and time lags in realisation of projects may lead to years of overall time lag between creating demand and supply following it and vice versa. Time lags could severely affect the solution of incremental investments. Time lags in solving the 2PCE problem might lead to the entire value chain being given up in favour of a competing technological approach and business model.

A fourth inhibiting factor is intrinsic to the substitute supply and substitute demand solutions: The ability to substitute reduces the threshold to invest, but it makes the investor an unreliable business partner for follow-on investors that want to do business with him. After all, there are substitutes. There would be a bargaining power asymmetry between a

⁶⁹ David Schlund, Simon Schulte, and Tobias Sprenger, 'The Who's Who of a Hydrogen Market Ramp-up: A Stakeholder Analysis for Germany', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 154 (1 February 2022): 111810, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111810>.

specialised supplier and a consumer who may substitute that specialised supply in favour of the latter. This belongs to the field of theory of incomplete contracts and is similar to the hold-up problem.⁷⁰

4.8 Solutions for the three parties chicken and the egg problem

Trabucchi covered the topic of how to solve the three parties chicken and the egg problem at length.⁷¹ We did not advance with research on this version of the chicken and the egg problem.

5. The Chicken and the egg problem in the nascent hydrogen economy

5.1 The value chains in the hydrogen economy

Green hydrogen is defined as hydrogen produced via water electrolysis with renewable energy input.⁷² This approach is pursued to avoid the greenhouse gas emissions associated with hydrogen from natural gas steam reforming. There are other ways to produce low greenhouse gas emission hydrogen, but green hydrogen is very important because production can be scaled up quickly with wind and photovoltaic (solar) energy. Electricity generation with wind and solar power is the first value chain level commonly associated with green hydrogen. The second level is usually water purification (often desalination) for the PEM electrolysis technology, but this level does not receive much attention because its technology is mature and its costs are relatively small. The third level is water electrolysis to separate hydrogen from oxygen. This level may include purification (especially dehumidification) of the hydrogen. The hydrogen has to be stored and transported and finally there's an end user level for the green hydrogen. Hydrogen is so far primarily used as material input (hydrogenation in oil refineries, ammonia and methanol production).⁷³ A future hydrogen value chain is expected to include green hydrogen use for (mostly high) temperature process heat and use as fuel for electricity grid backup powerplants (to bridge dark doldrum periods when wind and solar powerplants produce little output).⁷⁴

70 Y.-K. Che and J. Sakovics, 'The Hold-Up Problem', ESE Discussion Papers, 2006, https://www.pure.ed.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/18535269/Hold_up_problem.pdf.

71 Daniel Trabucchi, 'Let's Get a Two-Sided Platform Started: Tactics to Solve the Chicken and Egg Paradox', *Journal of Business Ecosystems (JBE)* 1, no. 1 (1 January 2020): 63–77, <https://doi.org/10.4018/JBE.2020010104>.

72 Incer-Valverde et al., "'Colors" of Hydrogen'.

73 IEA, 'Global Hydrogen Review 2024', 20.

74 IEA, 22.

Figure 2: Partial value chain of the green hydrogen economy, own work.

5.2 Current hydrogen availability and future hydrogen import plans in Germany

About 94% of current hydrogen production in Germany during 2023 was so-called grey hydrogen;⁷⁵ hydrogen produced by steam-reforming natural gas with carbon dioxide emitted to the atmosphere.

The federal government has written a national hydrogen strategy under the Merkel administration. It was upgraded with more ambitious targets and amended by a national hydrogen import strategy of the cabinet Scholz.⁷⁶ The German revised national hydrogen strategy explicitly calls for the creation of electrolyser capacity and additionally for green hydrogen imports. As of late 2024 the national hydrogen strategy assumes a 95 to 130 TWh hydrogen and derivatives consumption with 50 to 70% import share and an installed capacity of at least 10 GW electrolysis by the year 2030.⁷⁷ The installed electrolyser capacity in Germany was 0.1537 GW as of 13 Mai 2024 according to the Wasserstoff-Kompass.⁷⁸

The coalition contract for the new cabinet Merz includes support for green hydrogen, acceptance of different grades of hydrogen for the transition and support for the already planned European hydrogen pipeline infrastructure.⁷⁹

5.3 Cases of Chicken and the egg investment blockages in the hydrogen economy

The 2PCE problem occurs in the following pairings:

⁷⁵ 'Hochlauf der grünen Wasserstoffwirtschaft – wo steht Deutschland?', n.d., accessed 9 May 2025.

⁷⁶ BMWK-Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz, 'Importstrategie Wasserstoff und Wasserstoffderivate', accessed 15 April 2025,

<https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Publikationen/Energie/importstrategie-wasserstoff.html>.

⁷⁷ 'Fortschreibung Der Nationalen Wasserstoffstrategie', July 2023, 3 & 9,

https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Wasserstoff/Downloads/Fortschreibung.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4.

⁷⁸ 'Projektdatenbank Zum Elektrolyse-Monitor', 13 May 2024, https://www.wasserstoff-kompass.de/fileadmin/user_upload/img/home/2024-05-13_H2-Kompass_Projektdatenbank_01.xlsx.

⁷⁹ 'Verantwortung Für Deutschland', accessed 15 April 2025, <https://fragdenstaat.de/dokumente/258046-koalitionsvertrag-cdu-csu-spd-2025-entwurf/>.

- hydrogen producers & transportation service providers
- hydrogen storage providers and transportation providers
- hydrogen transportation service providers and hydrogen purchasers
- hydrogen storage service providers and hydrogen purchasers
- hydrogen fuel stations and hydrogen-fuelled road vehicle users

Figure 3 2PCE issues in the green hydrogen value chain, own work

We did not find evidence for a 2PCE problem between green electricity production and hydrogen electrolysis.

There was as of 2024 no 2PCE problem between electrolyser manufacturers and hydrogen producers due to electrolyser production overcapacities.⁸⁰

5.4 Why does the 2PCE problem strike only in some parts of the value chains?

5.4.1 Alternative demand

The electrical power supply is an important alternative demand for output in the green hydrogen supply chain, as wind and solar power producers easily find enough demand for their electricity besides the demand from electrolysis processes.

⁸⁰ Strategy&, 'Battle on the Global Electrolyzer Market', Strategy&, accessed 15 April 2025, <https://www.strategyand.pwc.com/de/en/industries/energy-utilities/electrolyzer-market.html>.

There is therefore no significant 2PCE problem between the green electricity investors and electrolysis investors. The former are certain of the alternative demand for electricity and are thus not facing the 2PCE problem.

5.4.2 Alternative supply

Molecular hydrogen (H₂) competes with other molecules that have elemental hydrogen such as Methane (CH₄) in its uses as material input. H₂ and CH₄ are substitutes in direct reduced iron (primary steel production) processes and can be mixed in such a process.⁸¹ It is possible to invest in technical installations and vehicles capable of using both hydrogen and substitutes. Examples are H₂-ready liquid natural gas port terminals, H₂-ready gas turbines, burners and direct reduced iron processes. It's also possible to generate H₂ from Methane on-site to provide H₂ supply to a H₂-only process. Potential investors for hydrogen-consuming processes could thus exploit the demand side substitute compatibility solution. This does on one hand encourage investment in some H₂-ready investment goods, but on the other side the potential hydrogen supply-side investors may remain uncertain about the demand for green hydrogen even after the demand side has invested.

5.5 Inhibitors of investment in the green hydrogen transformation other than the 2PCE problem

5.5.1 Questionable price competitiveness of hydrogen

Hydrogen production with renewable electricity supply and water is to date more expensive than hydrogen production via steam reforming of natural gas. Hydrogen is a substitute to natural gas in many applications, but natural gas is the cheaper input with natural gas prices as in 2020 or 2024 (about 5 to 50 EUR/MWh).⁸² A green hydrogen price of 2 EUR/kg seems optimistic, but this would correspond in thermal uses to approx. 50 EUR/MWh. The levelised cost of hydrogen of the winning bids in the first auction of the EU hydrogen bank was 5.3 to 13.5 EUR/kg by comparison.⁸³

Natural gas usage is very likely to become more expensive due to the EU Emissions Trading System, but future prices are not known for certain, though they were projected.

5.5.2 Skilled labour shortage

Germany faces a skilled labour shortage⁸⁴ due to demographics, low unemployment and other reasons. The skilled labour shortage is particularly severe in East Germany outside of large

81 'D5.4 Hydrogen use in Direct Reduction DR Plant - potentials for CO₂ mitigation in steel works.Pdf', accessed 15 April 2025, https://salcos.salzgitter-ag.com/fileadmin/footage/MEDIA/SZAG_microsites/salcos/2022/grinhy-20/downloads/deliverables/D5.4_Hydrogen_use_in_Direct_Reduction_DR_Plant_-_potentials_for_CO2_mitigation_in_steel_works.pdf.

82 'EU Natural Gas TTF - Price - Chart - Historical Data - News', accessed 15 April 2025, <https://tradingeconomics.com/commodity/eu-natural-gas>.

83 'Carbon Price Forecast 2030-2050: Assessing Market Stability & Future Challenges | Enerdata', 24 November 2023, 182, <https://www.enerdata.net/publications/executive-briefing/carbon-price-projections-eu-ets.html>.

84 'Arbeits- Und Fachkräftemangel Trotz Arbeitslosigkeit', Arbeitsmarkt Kompakt (Bundesagentur für Arbeit, March 2024), p.4, https://statistik.arbeitsagentur.de/DE/Statischer-Content/Statistiken/Themen-im-Fokus/Fachkraeftebedarf/Generische-Publikationen/Arbeits-und-Fachkraeftemangel-trotz-Arbeitslosigkeit.pdf?__blob=publicationFile.

cities. Businesses may choose to limit themselves to low risk business activities with higher expected rates than expected in the green hydrogen value chain in reaction to a severe scarcity of labour inputs. A transition from natural gas to hydrogen will be very difficult because of the shortage of qualified workers, which will become more severe in the next years, as many craftsmen are over the age of 50 years.⁸⁵

The potential hydrogen (derivatives) export countries are lacking qualified personnel as well. Namibia is a potentially important exporter of the hydrogen derivative ammonia, but it has a very small labour pool at about three million inhabitants,⁸⁶ almost all of them living far from the favourable locations for a hydrogen derivative export value chain. It's thus restricted in how much it can grow a hydrogen (and derivatives) production & export sector. Such limitations of potential hydrogen export countries add to the uncertainties of hydrogen supply for potential hydrogen consumers.

5.5.3 Expectation of future subsidies

Potential investors may expect higher subsidies for their investment in the future and thus refrain from launching their investment. This adds to the “value of waiting to invest”^{87,88,89}.

5.5.4 External economies of scale

Photovoltaic power cells, wind power installations as well as their peripheral equipment and services have displayed strong economies of scale. Multi-Megawatt Electrolysers of the PEM type are actually so-called stacks of small electrolyser boxes. Many of these boxes are needed for a large electrolyser facility and the German national hydrogen strategy projects the need for several Gigawatt of installed electrolyser capacity. The great quantity of PEM electrolyser boxes required for the transformation of industrial processes in the developed world to hydrogen gives good reason to expect strong economies of scale. A potential investor might refrain from investing early if the estimates show a rapid reduction of the relevant investment goods prices over the next few years.

The IEA wrote “If all announced projects are realised, electrolyser installed capital cost could be reduced by 50-55% by 2030 due to economies of scale and mass manufacturing.”⁹⁰

Sprenger et al. have described the economies of scale in parts of the green hydrogen supply chain in great detail.⁹¹

External economies of scale create another conundrum; some investors have to buy early so

85 Mathias Holzberger, Interview Stadtwerke Burg, 3 April 2025.

86 ‘UNdata | Record View | Total Population, Both Sexes Combined (Thousands)’, accessed 15 April 2025, <http://data.un.org/Data.aspx?q=namibia+population&d=PopDiv&f=variableID%3a12%3bcrID%3a516>.

87 McDonald and Siegel, ‘The Value of Waiting to Invest*’.

88 Morgan Kelly, ‘The Value of the Option to “Wait and See”’, *Economics Letters* 36, no. 2 (1 June 1991): 147–51, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1765\(91\)90180-S](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1765(91)90180-S).

89 Flora Biggins et al., ‘Green Hydrogen Investments: Investigating the Option to Wait’, *Energy* 241 (15 February 2022): 122842, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.122842>.

90 IEA, ‘Global Hydrogen Review 2024’, 77.

91 Tobias Sprenger, Amir Ashour Novirdoust, et al., ‘The Power of Scale Economies of Scale and the Hydrogen Value Chain’ (Cologne: Institute of Energy Economics at the University of Cologne, June 2023), https://www.ewi.uni-koeln.de/cms/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/20230602_EWI_The-Power-of-Scale_Economies-of-Scale-and-the-Hydrogen-Value-Chain.pdf.

the economies of scale get realised in the electrolyser manufacturing industry from learning.⁹² Future hydrogen markets would likely resemble systems of communicating pipes in both gaseous form (pipeline transportation) and liquid or derivative form (suitable for maritime shipping) and no intellectual property privileges apply. Thus, there's little pioneer advantage by becoming a dominant market player to be expected.

5.5.5 Uncertainties about optimal investment locations

There are uncertainties about whether electrolysis should happen close to consumption or close to renewable electrical power sources. This is contingent upon expansion of the electrical power grid, the general demand for electricity that may rise considerably due to electrification efforts and also the development of a national hydrogen pipeline grid.

6. Outlook

We published a first-ever summary of approaches how the two-party chicken and the egg (2PCE) problem can be overcome, including original contributions. We also explained why the 2PCE problem does not appear in some markets. Politicians, administrations and commercial companies may use this work to navigate the challenge and devise their own situation-specific strategy to overcome the 2PCE problem. This applies to many more value chains than just the green hydrogen value chain. Examples include sustainable fuels for maritime shipping and aviation, charging infrastructures for battery-electric vehicles, bioplastics and cultured meat.

We provided ways to overcome the 2PCE problem investment hold up, but further research is needed to explore what investments are optimal in the transition to a green hydrogen economy, particularly in regard to vertical integration and choice of locations.

Empirical research about how often which solution or combination of solutions was used to overcome the 2PCE problem is a possible topic for research. One might also determine the success rates and how long the delay between effort and success is with the various approaches and their combinations.

Finally, researchers could look out for examples of the two extended 2PCE problem versions that extend over more than two directly consecutive levels of the value chain.

7. Declaration of interest statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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⁹² Bianco and Hawila, 'Solving the Chicken and Egg Problem: Auctions for Green Hydrogen'.

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9. Bibliography

- A., Amish. ‘A Lot of Firsts in the India Green Ammonia Auction’, June 2024. <https://www.vnzinsights.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Indias-Green-Ammonia-Auction-SIGHT-Tender.pdf>.
- Allain, Marie-Laure, Claire Chambolle, Patrick Rey, and Sabrina Teyssier. ‘Vertical Integration as a Source of Hold-up: An Experiment’. *European Economic Review* 137 (1 August 2021): 103783. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.euroecorev.2021.103783>.
- Allain, M.-L., C. Chambolle, and P. Rey. ‘Vertical Integration as a Source of Hold-Up’. *Review of Economic Studies* 83, no. 1 (2016): 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1093/restud/rdv035>.
- ‘Arbeits- Und Fachkräftemangel Trotz Arbeitslosigkeit’. Arbeitsmarkt Kompakt. Bundesagentur für Arbeit, March 2024. https://statistik.arbeitsagentur.de/DE/Statischer-Content/Statistiken/Themen-im-Fokus/Fachkraeftebedarf/Generische-Publikationen/Arbeits-und-Fachkraeftemangel-trotz-Arbeitslosigkeit.pdf?__blob=publicationFile.
- argus media. ‘Shell Venture Eyes Creating Hydrogen Supply and Demand’, 11 October 2021. <https://www.argusmedia.com/en/news-and-insights/latest-market-news/2262465-shell-venture-eyes-creating-hydrogen-supply-and-demand>.
- Arnaiz del Pozo, Carlos, and Schalk Cloete. ‘Techno-Economic Assessment of Blue and Green Ammonia as Energy Carriers in a Low-Carbon Future’. *Energy Conversion and Management* 255 (March 2022): 115312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2022.115312>.
- Bataille, Chris, Seton Stiebert, and Jonas Algers. ‘Triggering Investment in First-of-a-Kind and Early Near-Zero Emissions Industrial Facilities’. Morningside Campus Status Updates. Center on Global Energy Policy at Columbia SIPA, 1 August 2024. <https://www.energypolicy.columbia.edu/publications/triggering-investment-in-first-of-a-kind-and-early-near-zero-emissions-industrial-facilities/>.
- Bento, Nuno. ‘Building and Interconnecting Hydrogen Networks: Insights from the Electricity and Gas Experience in Europe’. *Energy Policy* 36, no. 8 (1 August 2008): 3019–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2008.04.007>.
- Bianco, Emanuele, and Diala Hawila. ‘Solving the Chicken and Egg Problem: Auctions for Green Hydrogen’. *IRENA Newsletter* (blog), 12 September 2021. <https://www.irena.org/News/expertinsights/2021/Sep/Auctions-for-Green-Hydrogen>.
- Biggins, Flora, Mohit Kataria, Diarmid Roberts, and Dr Solomon Brown. ‘Green Hydrogen Investments: Investigating the Option to Wait’. *Energy* 241 (15 February 2022): 122842. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.122842>.
- Böllerey, Timo. ‘The 2nd H2Global Hydrogen Auction’. 26 March 2025. <https://mission-hydrogen.com/webinarlibrary/>.
- ‘Bundesnetzagentur - Wasserstoff-Kernnetz’. Accessed 15 April 2025. <https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/DE/Fachthemen/ElektrizitaetundGas/Wasserstoff/Kernnetz/start.html>.
- Burke, Andrew F., Jingyuan Zhao, and Lewis M. Fulton. ‘Projections of the Costs of Light-Duty Battery-Electric and Fuel Cell Vehicles (2020–2040) and Related Economic Issues’. *Research in Transportation Economics* 105 (1 July 2024): 101440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2024.101440>.
- ‘Carbon Price Forecast 2030-2050: Assessing Market Stability & Future Challenges | Enerdata’, 24 November 2023. <https://www.enerdata.net/publications/executive-briefing/carbon-price-projections-eu-ets.html>.
- Chan, Kar Hoong, Lee Lee Chong, Tuan Hock Ng, and Wan Ling Ong. ‘A Model of Green Investment Decision Making for Societal Well-Being’. *Heliyon* 8, no. 8 (1 August 2022): e10024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e10024>.
- Che, Y.-K., and J. Sakovics. ‘The Hold-Up Problem’, ESE Discussion Papers, 2006. https://www.pure.ed.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/18535269/Hold_up_problem.pdf.
- Choi, Jay Pil. ‘Herd Behavior, the “Penguin Effect,” and the Suppression of Informational Diffusion: An Analysis of Informational Externalities and Payoff Interdependency’. *The RAND Journal of Economics* 28, no. 3 (1997): 407–25. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2556022>.
- ‘Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change’. Geneva, Switzerland: International Panel on Climate Change, 20 March 2023. https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_SYR_FullVolume.pdf.

- ‘COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS’, 16 March 2023. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52023DC0156>.
- ‘D5.4_Hydrogen_use_in_Direct_Reduction_DR_Plant_-_potentials_for_CO2_mitigation_in_steel_works.Pdf’. Accessed 15 April 2025. https://salcos.salzgitter-ag.com/fileadmin/footage/MEDIA/SZAG_microsites/salcos/2022/grinhy-20/downloads/deliverables/D5.4_Hydrogen_use_in_Direct_Reduction_DR_Plant_-_potentials_for_CO2_mitigation_in_steel_works.pdf.
- DIRECTIVE 2003/87/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL (2003). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32003L0087>.
- Dollery, Brian, and Joe Wallis. ‘The Theory of Market Failure and Policy Making in Contemporary Local Government’, March 2001. https://www.une.edu.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0010/67816/econwp01-6.pdf.
- ‘EU Natural Gas TTF - Price - Chart - Historical Data - News’. Accessed 15 April 2025. <https://tradingeconomics.com/commodity/eu-natural-gas>.
- Everfuel press releases. ‘Everfuel Signs Letter of Intent with German Industrial Offtaker for Initial Supply of 10,000 Tons of Green Hydrogen per Year’, 8 May 2024. <https://www.everfuel.com/news/everfuel-signs-letter-of-intent-with-german-industrial-offtaker-for-initial-supply-of-10000-tons-of-green-hydrogen-per-year/>.
- Export Credit Guarantees of the Federal Government. ‘Export Credit Guarantees of the Federal Government’. Accessed 15 April 2025. <https://www.exportkreditgarantien.de/en>.
- ‘Fortschreibung Der Nationalen Wasserstoffstrategie’, July 2023. https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Wasserstoff/Downloads/Fortschreibung.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4.
- Franke, Katja, Joshua Fragoso Garcia, Christoph Kleinschmitt, and Frank Sensfuß. ‘Assessing Worldwide Future Potentials of Renewable Electricity Generation: Installable Capacity, Full Load Hours and Costs’. *Renewable Energy* 226, no. C (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.120>.
- Fuel Cell Works. ‘Understanding the Realities of Hydrogen: Key Insights From the IEA Report’, 16 January 2025. <https://fuelcellworks.com/2025/01/16/hydrogen/understanding-the-realities-of-hydrogen-key-insights-from-the-iea-report>.
- ‘Global Hydrogen Review 2024’. International Energy Agency, October 2024. <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/89c1e382-dc59-46ca-aa47-9f7d41531ab5/GlobalHydrogenReview2024.pdf>.
- Graul, Hanna. ‘Re: Re: Frage zu Hintco’, 3 June 2025.
- Green Car Congress. ‘IDTechEx Predicts Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles to Be 4% of the Zero Emission Solution in 2044’, 7 January 2024. <https://www.greencarcongress.com/2024/01/20240107-fcev.html>.
- ‘Green Power MSH2’. Accessed 15 April 2025. <https://www.stadtwerke-hettstedt.de/ihr-service/downloads/energietagung.html?file=files/downloads/1-energietagung/paesi-seg-green-power-msh2.pdf>.
- H2-news.de. ‘Henne-Ei-Problem’. Accessed 15 April 2025. <https://h2-news.de/glossary/henne-ei/>.
- ‘Hintco Factsheet’. Accessed 9 April 2025. <https://cdn.sanity.io/files/u4w9plcz/production/8506bc6f24909ba96b6748f3fb0b28ab914607da.pdf>.
- ‘Hochlauf der grünen Wasserstoffwirtschaft – wo steht Deutschland?’, n.d. Accessed 9 May 2025.
- Holzberger, Mathias. Interview Stadtwerke Burg, 3 April 2025.
- ‘Hydrogen in Latin America’. International Energy Agency, August 2021. <https://www.iea.org/reports/hydrogen-in-latin-america>.
- IEA. ‘Global Hydrogen Review 2024’, 10 January 2024. <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-hydrogen-review-2024>.
- Incer-Valverde, Jimena, Amira Korayem, George Tsatsaronis, and Tatiana Morosuk. ‘“Colors” of Hydrogen: Definitions and Carbon Intensity’. *Energy Conversion and Management* 291 (1 September 2023): 117294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2023.117294>.
- ‘Infrastructure12.Pdf’. Accessed 15 April 2025. <https://people.bu.edu/nalink/papers/Infrastructure12.pdf>.
- Kelly, Morgan. ‘The Value of the Option to “Wait and See”’. *Economics Letters* 36, no. 2 (1 June 1991): 147–51. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1765\(91\)90180-S](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1765(91)90180-S).
- Klimaschutz, BMWK-Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und. ‘Importstrategie Wasserstoff und Wasserstoffderivate’. Accessed 15 April 2025. <https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Publikationen/Energie/importstrategie-wasserstoff.html>.

- Knight, Frank Hyneman. *Risk, Uncertainty and Profit*. Boston and New York: Houghton Mifflin Company The Riverside Press Cambridge, 1921.
<https://fraser.stlouisfed.org/files/docs/publications/books/risk/riskuncertaintyprofit.pdf>.
- Liu, Jing-Yue, Quan Lei, Ruojin Li, and Yue-Jun Zhang. 'Resistance or Motivation? Impact of Climate Risk on Corporate Greenwashing: An Empirical Study of Chinese Enterprises'. *Global Finance Journal* 62 (1 September 2024): 101030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfj.2024.101030>.
- Mäkitie, Tuukka, Janis Danebergs, Jens Hanson, and Eirik Gjelsvik Medbø. 'Solving the Chicken and Egg Problem in Maritime Hydrogen Value Chains in Western Norway'. FME NTRANS Report. Norwegian Centre for Energy Transition Strategies, 2021.
<https://www.ntnu.edu/documents/1276062818/1283878281/Solving+the+chicken+and+egg+problem+i+n+maritime+hydrogen+value+chains+in+Western+Norway.pdf/>.
- McDonald, Robert, and Daniel Siegel. 'The Value of Waiting to Invest*'. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 101, no. 4 (1 November 1986): 707–27. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1884175>.
- Melendez, M., and A. Milibrandt. 'Hydrogen Infrastructure Transition Analysis'. National Renewable Energy Laboratory, January 2006. <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy06osti38351.pdf>.
- Mnyanda, Lukanyo. 'Cracking Green Hydrogen's Chicken and Egg Problem'. *Financial Times*, 12 June 2024, sec. Hydrogen power. <https://www.ft.com/content/d3102a61-368e-4ec6-8de3-833f4c62e7ba>.
- 'Net-Zero Tracker', 8 April 2025. <https://www.climatewatchdata.org/net-zero-tracker>.
- 'Northern-Ireland-Hydrogen-Roadmap-and-Technology-Options-Scoping-Study.Pdf'. Accessed 15 April 2025.
<https://matrixni.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/Northern-Ireland-Hydrogen-Roadmap-and-Technology-Options-Scoping-Study.pdf>.
- '(PDF) Risk As Feelings'. *ResearchGate*, 22 October 2024.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/230896630_Risk_As_Feelings.
- 'Projektdatenbank Zum Elektrolyse-Monitor', 13 May 2024. https://www.wasserstoff-kompass.de/fileadmin/user_upload/img/home/2024-05-13_H2-Kompass_Projektdatenbank_01.xlsx.
- Qi, Ning, Kaidi Huang, Zhiyuan Fan, and Bolun Xu. 'Long-Term Energy Management for Microgrid with Hybrid Hydrogen-Battery Energy Storage: A Prediction-Free Coordinated Optimization Framework'. *Applied Energy* 377 (1 January 2025): 124485. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.124485>.
- 'Renewable and Low-Carbon Hydrogen', n.d.
 ResearchGate. '(PDF) Rational Choice'. Accessed 15 April 2025.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227458334_Rational_Choice.
- Rodrik, Dani. 'INDUSTRIAL POLICY FOR THE TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY', September 2004.
- Salzgitter AG press releases. 'GrInHy2.0: Grüner Wasserstoff Für Grüne Stahlproduktion', 17 October 2022.
<https://www.salzgitter-ag.com/de/newsroom/pressemeldungen/details/grinhy20-gruener-wasserstoff-fuer-gruene-stahlproduktion-20194.html>.
- Scharfstein, David S., and Jeremy C. Stein. 'Herd Behavior and Investment'. *The American Economic Review* 80, no. 3 (1990): 465–79.
- Schlund, David, Simon Schulte, and Tobias Sprenger. 'The Who's Who of a Hydrogen Market Ramp-up: A Stakeholder Analysis for Germany'. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 154 (1 February 2022): 111810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111810>.
- Simon, Frédéric. 'EU Bets on Blue Hydrogen "to Break Chicken-and-Egg Problem"'. Euractiv, 9 December 2020. <https://www.euractiv.com/section/energy-environment/news/eu-bets-on-blue-hydrogen-to-break-chicken-and-egg-problem/>.
- Song, Fenghua, Anjan Thakor, and Robert Quinn. 'Purpose, Profit and Social Pressure'. *Journal of Financial Intermediation* 55 (1 July 2023): 101031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfi.2023.101031>.
- Sperling, Daniel. *New Transportation Fuels: A Strategic Approach towards Technological Change*. University of California Press, 1988.
- Sprenger, Tobias, Amir Ashour Novirdourst, Michael Moritz, and Patricia Wild. 'The Power of Scale Economies of Scale and the Hydrogen Value Chain'. Institute of Energy Economics at the University of Cologne (EWI), 6 January 2023. https://www.ewi.uni-koeln.de/cms/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/20230602_EWI_The-Power-of-Scale_Economies-of-Scale-and-the-Hydrogen-Value-Chain.pdf.
- Sprenger, Tobias, Amir Ashour Novirdoust, Michael Moritz, and Patricia Wild. 'The Power of Scale Economies of Scale and the Hydrogen Value Chain'. Cologne: Institute of Energy Economics at the University of Cologne, June 2023. https://www.ewi.uni-koeln.de/cms/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/20230602_EWI_The-Power-of-Scale_Economies-of-Scale-and-the-Hydrogen-Value-Chain.pdf.
- Strategy&. 'Battle on the Global Electrolyzer Market'. Strategy&. Accessed 15 April 2025.
<https://www.strategyand.pwc.com/de/en/industries/energy-utilities/electrolyzer-market.html>.

- . ‘Battle on the Global Electrolyzer Market’. Strategy&. Accessed 15 April 2025.
<https://www.strategyand.pwc.com/de/en/industries/energy-utilities/electrolyzer-market.html>.
- TotalEnergies.com. ‘TotalEnergies, Air Liquide, VINCI and a Group of International Companies Launch the World’s Largest Clean Hydrogen Infrastructure Fund’, 10 January 2021.
<https://totalenergies.com/media/news/press-releases/launch-of-the-worlds-largest-clean-hydrogen-infrastructure-fund>.
- Trabucchi, Daniel. ‘Let’s Get a Two-Sided Platform Started: Tactics to Solve the Chicken and Egg Paradox’. *Journal of Business Ecosystems (JBE)* 1, no. 1 (1 January 2020): 63–77.
<https://doi.org/10.4018/JBE.2020010104>.
- ‘UK Hydrogen Strategy’, 17 August 2021.
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/64c7e8bad8b1a70011b05e38/UK-Hydrogen-Strategy_web.pdf.
- ‘UNdata | Record View | Total Population, Both Sexes Combined (Thousands)’. Accessed 15 April 2025.
<http://data.un.org/Data.aspx?q=namibia+population&d=PopDiv&f=variableID%3a12%3bcrID%3a516>.
- ‘Verantwortung Für Deutschland’. Accessed 15 April 2025. <https://fragdenstaat.de/dokumente/258046-koalitionsvertrag-cdu-csu-spd-2025-entwurf/>.
- ‘VNG Und HyCC Planen Erzeugung von Grünem Wasserstoff in Lutherstadt Wittenberg | VNG AG’. Accessed 9 May 2025. <https://www.vng.de/de/newsroom/2024-12-04-vng-und-hycc-planen-erzeugung-von-gruenem-wasserstoff-lutherstadt-wittenberg>.
- White, Lee V., David Gourlay, and Emma Aisbett. ‘Chapter 1.2 Potential Market Failures Inhibiting the Development of a Green Hydrogen Export Industry’. In *Towards Hydrogen Infrastructure : Advances and Challenges in Preparing for the Hydrogen Economy*, 39–58. Elsevier, 2023.
- Wolf, Charles. ‘Markets or Governments: Choosing between Imperfect Alternatives’. The Rand Corporation, September 1986. <https://www.rand.org/content/dam/rand/pubs/notes/2006/N2505.pdf> pp 14-24.